

Sufficient condition for compression of morbidity: Examination of the transition rates in the illness-death model

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Introduction

Over the past decades, the life expectancy (LE) in many countries of the world has been increasing. More than 40 years ago, rheumatologist James F. Fries examined whether increasing life time comes along with shortening the period of morbidity at the end of the life. For reducing the life expectancy with morbidity (LEM), Fries coined the term “compression of morbidity” (COM) [Fries 1980].

Recently, it could be shown that analyzing the COM hypothesis is closely related to the illness-death model [Brinks 2018], which is shown in Figure 1: A subject of the population under consideration can be in exactly one of the states *Healthy*, *Morbid* or *Dead*. During the course of life, subjects may change the states according to the transitions indicated by arrows in Figure 1. The incidence rate λ of morbidity and the mortality rates μ_0 and μ_1 depend on two different time scales, calendar time t and age a .

Figure 1: Illness-death model. Subjects in the population can either be *Healthy*, *Morbid* or *Dead*. The transition rates between the states (incidence λ and the mortality rates μ_0 , μ_1) depend on the calendar time t (period) and on the age a .

Using the terminology of the illness-death model, it could be shown in [Brinks 2018] that the LEM for a birth cohort born at calendar time t_0 , can be expressed as

$$LEM(t_0) = \int_0^{\infty} p(t_0 + \tau, \tau) \exp\left(\int_0^{\tau} \{p \times \mu_1 + (1 - p) \times \mu_0\}(t_0 + x, x) dx\right) d\tau \quad (1)$$

where $p(t, a)$ refers to the percentage of subjects aged a at time t who are alive and in the *Morbid* state, i.e. p is the age-specific prevalence of morbidity at time t .

In this article, a sufficient condition for a decreasing LEM in terms of the rates of the illness-death model is derived, which partly answers the question under which conditions compression of morbidity can be achieved. Finally, an example from the context of the need for long-term care is given.

Analytical considerations

Starting from Equation (1) we note that the LEM can be written as

$$LEM(t_0) = \int_0^{\infty} P_{01}(0, \tau; t_0) d\tau. \quad (2)$$

We use the terminology $P_{0j}(0, x; t_0)$ for the probability of someone being born at $(t, a) = (t_0, 0)$ in state 0 is in state j at $(t, a) = (t_0+x, x)$, $j = 0, 1$ referring to the state *Healthy* and *Morbid*, respectively. The Kolmogorov forward equations for P_{01} yields

$$P_{01}(0, \tau; t_0) = \int_0^{\tau} P_{00}(0, x; t_0) \lambda(t_0 + x, x) \exp\left(-\int_x^{\tau} \mu_1(t_0 + \xi, \xi) d\xi\right) dx. \quad (3)$$

Inserting

$$P_{00}(0, x; t_0) = \exp\left(-\int_0^x \{\lambda + \mu_0\}(t_0 + \xi, \xi) d\xi\right)$$

into Equation (3) and substituting the combined expression into Equation (2) yields

$$LEM(t_0) = \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\tau} \exp\left(-\int_0^x \{\lambda + \mu_0\}(t_0 + \xi, \xi) d\xi\right) \lambda(t_0 + x, x) \exp\left(-\int_x^{\tau} \mu_1(t_0 + \xi, \xi) d\xi\right) dx d\tau. \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) shows that the LEM is completely determined by the transition rates λ , μ_0 and μ_1 of the illness-death model in Figure 1.

For deriving a sufficient condition for a declining LEM, let u , v , w denote the three factors inside the double integral in Equation (4). Then, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} u &= u \times \left(-\int_0^x \{\dot{\lambda} + \dot{\mu}_0\}(t_0 + \xi, \xi) d\xi\right), \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} v &= \dot{\lambda}(t_0 + x, x) = \frac{\dot{\lambda}(t_0 + x, x)}{\lambda(t_0 + x, x)} \lambda(t_0 + x, x), \text{ and} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} w &= w \times \left(-\int_x^{\tau} \dot{\mu}_1(t_0 + \xi, \xi) d\xi\right), \end{aligned}$$

where the dot notation for the partial derivative with respect to calendar time t has been used, e.g. $\dot{\lambda} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \lambda$.

Then, the Leibniz' rule for differentiation under the integral in Equation (4) and subsequent application of the product rule implies

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} LEM(t_0) = \int_0^\infty \int_0^\tau \{u \times v \times w\}(x, \tau, t_0) \left[\frac{\dot{\lambda}(t_0+x, x)}{\lambda(t_0+x, x)} - \int_0^x \{\dot{\lambda} + \dot{\mu}_0\}(t_0 + \xi, \xi) d\xi - \int_x^\tau \dot{\mu}_1(t_0 + \xi, \xi) d\xi \right] dx d\tau. \quad (5)$$

The term in the square brackets in Equation (5) is important for the sign of the change $\partial LEM / \partial t_0$ of the LEM, which motivates the definition

$$\Psi(x, \tau, t_0) = \frac{\dot{\lambda}(t_0+x, x)}{\lambda(t_0+x, x)} - \int_0^x \{\dot{\lambda} + \dot{\mu}_0\}(t_0 + \xi, \xi) d\xi - \int_x^\tau \dot{\mu}_1(t_0 + \xi, \xi) d\xi. \quad (6)$$

Note that it holds $0 \leq x \leq \tau$ in the defining Equation (6). Since the functions u , v , and w are non-negative, a decreasing LEM can be guaranteed, if Ψ is strictly negative, which yields following sufficient condition for $\partial LEM / \partial t_0 < 0$:

$$\text{If } \Psi(x, \tau, t_0) < 0 \text{ for all } 0 \leq x \leq \tau, \text{ then } \frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} LEM(t_0) < 0.$$

The condition $\Psi(x, \tau, t_0) < 0$ for all $0 \leq x \leq \tau$ is not a *necessary* condition, because of the weighting factor $\varphi = u \times v \times w$ in front of Ψ in Equation (5): a positive Ψ with low weight φ can be compensated by negative Ψ with a higher weight φ during integration such that $\partial LEM / \partial t_0 < 0$.

Usually, the mortality rates μ_0 and μ_1 have a negative time trend due to progress in medicine and prevention of accidents. Thus, the integrals regarding the mortality rates will be negative. In order to have $\Psi < 0$ the contributions by the incidence rate λ need to be more negative, which is examined in the next section.

Example

This section provides a hypothetical example with exponential transition rates λ , μ_0 and μ_1 given by following expressions

$$\lambda(t, a) = \exp(\alpha_\lambda + \beta_\lambda a + \gamma_\lambda t), \quad (7a)$$

$$\mu_j(t, a) = \exp(\alpha_j + \beta_j a + \gamma_j t), \quad j = 0, 1. \quad (7b)$$

The coefficients α , β , γ for each of the rates λ , μ_0 and μ_1 are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Coefficients α , β , γ of the transition rates following the exponential rule given by Equations (7).

	Coefficient		
	α	β	γ
Mortality μ_0	-10.5	0.100	$\ln(0.99)$
Mortality μ_1	-9.8	0.101	$\ln(0.98)$
Incidence λ	-6.5	0.370	-0.3515

Calculation of prevalence p , LE and LEM for two birth cohorts, one born at $t_0 = 0$ and another born half a year later at $t_0 = 0.5$, follows the method described in [Brinks 2018]. The resulting age-specific prevalences for the two birth cohorts are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Age-specific prevalences p of morbidity for two birth cohorts born in the years $t_0 = 0$ (black solid line) and half a year later at $t_0 = 0.5$ (blue dashed line).

The resulting LE and LEM for the birth cohorts are presented in Table 2. We see that the LE for the first birth cohort is 82.32 (years) and 82.38 half a year later. LEM reduces from 8.77 (years) to 7.5. The percentage of life spent with morbidity decreases from 10.7% to 9.11%. Thus, we observe an absolute and a relative compression of morbidity.

Table 2: Life expectancy (LE), life expectancy with morbidity (LEM) and proportion of morbid life (LEM/LE) for two birth cohorts born at $t_0 = 0$ and $t_0 = 0.5$ in the example described in the text.

	Year	
	$t_0 = 0$	$t_0 = 0.5$
Life expectancy (LE) (years)	82.32	82.38
Life expectancy with morbidity (LEM)	8.77	7.50
LEM/LE	10.7%	9.11%

As we are interested in the condition $\Psi(x, \tau, t_0) < 0$ for all $0 \leq x \leq \tau$, we examine the function Ψ for the rates in Equations (7a) and (7b) in this example. Inserting Eqs (7) into Eq. (6) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi(x, \tau, t_0) = & \gamma_\lambda - \delta_\lambda \exp(\gamma_\lambda t_0) \left[\exp(\{\beta_\lambda + \gamma_\lambda\}x) - 1 \right] \\ & - \delta_0 \exp(\gamma_0 t_0) \left[\exp(\{\beta_0 + \gamma_0\}x) - 1 \right] \\ & - \delta_1 \exp(\gamma_1 t_0) \left[\exp(\{\beta_1 + \gamma_1\}\tau) - \exp(\{\beta_1 + \gamma_1\}x) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{with } \delta = \frac{\gamma}{\beta + \gamma} \exp(\alpha).$$

Usually, we have $\gamma_0, \gamma_1 < 0$ in Eq. (7b) (which implies that $LE(t_0)$ increases for increasing t_0) as well as $\gamma_\lambda \leq 0$ in Eq. (7a). Increase of the rates with age a usually is positive for all three rates, i.e., $\beta > 0$. If we have $\beta + \gamma > 0$ for all three rates, then $x \mapsto \exp(\{\beta + \gamma\}x)$ is monotonically increasing. Since $0 \leq x \leq \tau$, all expressions of Equation (8) in square brackets $[\]$ are non-negative and all factors $\delta \exp(\gamma t_0)$ in front of

the λ are negative. In order to have $\Psi(x, \tau, t_0) < 0$ for all $0 \leq x \leq \tau$, the solitary γ_λ at the start of Eq. (8) has to be more negative to compensate for the three remaining positive terms ($-\delta \exp[\dots]$). In the example with exponential transition rates (Eq. (7a) and (7b) with values given in Table 1), this is guaranteed by choosing $\gamma_\lambda = -0.3515$, which means a strong negative trend in the incidence.

Conclusion

In this article, a sufficient criterion for absolute compression of life expectancy with morbidity (LEM) has been derived. The illness-death model and the associated transition rates turn out to be essential for a rigorous analytical examination. The sufficient condition focusses on the sign of a function Ψ given in Equation (6).

To demonstrate the usefulness of the mathematical framework, an example was given, where the life expectancy (LE) increased and the LEM decreased (absolute and relative compression). In the example, this is possible by an enormous temporal decrease of the incidence rate ($\gamma_\lambda < -0.3$).

References

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